

NATIONAL PHYSICAL LABORATORY

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Certificate of Calibration

0478

THERMOMETERS
20473E, 15480E, 17004E

This certificate is issued in accordance with the laboratory accreditation requirements of the United Kingdom Accreditation Service. It provides traceability of measurement to the SI system of units and/or to units of measurement realised at the National Physical Laboratory or other recognised national metrology institutes. This certificate may not be reproduced other than in full, except with the prior written approval of the issuing laboratory.

FOR: Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
Building 146
Cranfield University
Cranfield
Bedfordshire
MK43 0AL

For the attention of Dr Hannah Price

DESCRIPTION: Three 50 Ω platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs)

IDENTIFICATION: Type: E102BL (Plate), E102AL (Plate), E102AL (Plate)
Serial No: 20473E, 15480E, 17004E

PREVIOUS CERTIFICATES: 2017120149-2 dated 17 January 2018
2015110037-1 dated 10 December 2015
2017120149-1 dated 17 January 2018

DATES OF CALIBRATION: 17 October to 21 October 2019

Reference: 2019100005-1

Date of issue: 8 November 2019

Checked by:

Signed:

Name: Mr P A Carroll

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(Authorised Signatory)

on behalf of NPLML

This certificate is consistent with the capabilities that are included in Appendix C of the MRA drawn up by the CIPM. Under the MRA, all participating institutes recognise the validity of each other's calibration and measurement certificates for the quantities, ranges and measurement uncertainties specified in Appendix C (for details see <http://www.bipm.org>).

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Continuation Sheet

MEASUREMENTS

The thermometers were calibrated in a test chamber, in air, by comparison against reference platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs).

Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of the reference thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) through NPL Temperature Standards. As requested the PRTs were monitored using a precision resistance bridge with traceability to national standards, using an excitation current of 2.8 mA. At each generated condition a time of not less than 60 minutes was allowed for temperature to equilibrate. A set of 10 readings recorded at 2 minute intervals was then taken from the instruments under test.

The values of the applied conditions are shown in the first column of the table below. The values measured from the instruments under test are then quoted with their equivalent expanded uncertainties, shown in degrees Celsius. This quoted uncertainty relates to the period of the calibration and is not an indication of the long-term stability of the instruments.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were 23 °C ± 3 °C and less than 80 % relative humidity.

Applied Condition	Test Thermometers			
	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 20473E	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 15480E	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 17004E	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement
°C	Ω	Ω	Ω	°C
-60.57 #	38.090	38.057	38.067	±0.08
-50.11 #	40.183	40.148	40.161	±0.08
-40.14	42.172	42.135	42.151	±0.08
-30.06	44.173	44.134	44.154	±0.08
-19.99	46.168	46.126	46.151	±0.05
-10.02	48.135	48.090	48.120	±0.05
-0.05	50.095	50.048	50.081	±0.05
+9.97	52.056	52.009	52.046	±0.05
+19.98	54.011	53.963	54.004	±0.05
+30.07	55.972	55.923	55.967	±0.05
+40.05	57.908	57.857	57.905	±0.05
+50.00	59.831	59.778	59.831	±0.05

NOTE: # Points below -40 °C are outside the range of UKAS accreditation of NPL for air temperature

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UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the applied condition represents a combination of the uncertainties arising from calibration and estimated stability of the reference standards, and from the method of transfer to the instrument under test.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the uncertainty of the applied condition, the resolution of the instrument and its standard deviation for the period of the test. An uncertainty contribution has been included for rounding to give results an equivalent resolution of 0.01 °C.

The reported expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95 %. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.